

Enhanced evaporative cooling using additively manufactured PLA–wood composite lattices

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ABSTRACT

Evaporative cooling technologies are increasingly recognized as energy-efficient and sustainable alternatives to conventional air-conditioning systems. In this study, five evaporative cooling pads, four with lattice geometries and one conventional grid-type reference pad, were designed and fabricated through additive manufacturing using a polylactic acid (PLA)-wood composite, then characterized and experimentally evaluated under controlled inlet air conditions. Material characterization revealed a rough mesoporous morphology and intermediate wettability, favouring capillary-driven water retention. Among the tested designs, the octagonal lattice geometry exhibited the largest air–water contact surface, achieving the greatest temperature drop (19.7 °C) and wet bulb effectiveness (0.93), thereby demonstrating superior performance. This geometry was subsequently scaled up into a full-scale prototype incorporating an integrated water distribution system. Statistical analysis confirmed that both inlet air temperature and airflow rate had a significant effect on cooling performance, with coefficients of determination above 0.98. The energy analysis of the prototype showed that the cooling capacity increased up to 800 W, while the energy efficiency ratio ranged between 7 and 87 depending on operating conditions. The findings emphasize the strong connection between material properties, lattice geometry, and energy performance, supporting this design to optimize sustainable evaporative cooling systems for building applications.

1. Introduction

Global warming has led to a significant rise in average global temperatures over the past decades, with profound consequences for climate stability and human comfort [1]. The increasing frequency of heatwaves is accelerating global energy demand, intensifying the need for space cooling in the building sector [2]. Currently, buildings account for nearly 30 % of global final energy consumption, contributing significantly to global CO₂ emissions. Notably, projections indicate that cooling demand could double by 2050 in warmer regions, underscoring the urgent need for innovative solutions [3]. As a result, energy-efficient systems are being developed to mitigate the environmental impacts of climate change, especially within the framework of nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (NZEBs) [4,5].

Conventional vapor-compression systems, while dominant in the

cooling market, are highly energy-intensive and rely on refrigerants with considerable global warming potential, posing both environmental and operational challenges [6]. In view of the current situation, evaporative cooling (EC) systems have emerged as a promising low-energy alternative, leveraging the natural process of water evaporation to provide thermal comfort without relying on refrigerants [7]. These systems are increasingly applied in the building sector, integrating evaporative cooling strategies into building envelopes can enable electricity consumption reductions of approximately 50 % during the hottest months [8]. A specific application is direct evaporative cooling (DEC), where air is forced through wetted media, commonly cooling pads, promoting heat and mass transfer between air and water to achieve temperature reduction [9].

The performance of DEC systems is strongly influenced by the characteristics of the evaporative materials. Recently, several experimental studies have compared the suitability of different natural porous

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Nomenclature	
EER	energy efficiency ratio [-]
h	specific enthalpy [kJ·kg ⁻¹]
\dot{m}	mass flow [kg/s]
P	pressure [Pa]
\dot{Q}	heat transfer rate [kW]
Q	energy [J]
R	contact surface-to-volume ratio [cm ⁻¹]
S_c	contact surface for air-water [cm ²]
t	time [min]
T	temperature [°C]
V	external volume [cm ³]
\dot{V}	volumetric air flow rate [m ³ /h]
w_d	dry weight [g]
\dot{W}	electric energy consumption [W]
\hat{Y}	estimated output value
<i>Greek letters</i>	
Δ	differential
β_n	estimated coefficient
ε	effectiveness [-]
θ	contact angle [°]
ω	humidity ratio [kg·kg ⁻¹]
<i>Subscripts</i>	
aux	auxiliary
d	dew point
fan	fan
i	inlet
l	latent
max	maximum
o	outlet
pump	pump
s	sensible
wb	wet bulb
<i>Acronyms</i>	
ADSA-P	axisymmetric drop shape analysis – perimeter
AHU	air handling unit
AM	additive manufacturing
ANOVA	analysis of variance
DEC	direct evaporative cooling
EC	evaporative cooling
FC	flow conditioner
HVAC	heating, ventilation and air conditioning
HX	heat exchangers
NZEBs	nearly zero-energy
MEX	material extrusion
PLA	polylactic acid
PT	pitot tube
SEM	scanning electron spectroscopy

materials for DEC such as eucalyptus fibres, cellulose, luffa, and coconut, owing to their high water absorption capacity, which enhances air–water interaction [10–12]. The influence of pore morphology and contact angle (wettability) in porous media has been thoroughly analysed in previous heat and mass-transfer studies [13]. However, while natural porous materials have demonstrated good evaporative performance, their long-term durability, often limit their practical application in building systems. Consequently, recent studies investigated polymeric and composite materials, which offer improved structural robustness and controllable surface properties [14]. Among these, polymeric composites incorporating sustainable fillers have shown notably higher water adsorption capacity compared to pure polymers. For instance, formulations containing processed waste exhibited up to 80 % higher adsorption than neat polylactic acid (PLA) and around 13 % greater than other polymer-based composites [15].

Additive Manufacturing (AM) has emerged as a powerful tool for the design and fabrication of complex geometries, enabling the use of polymeric materials with high precision, flexibility, and reduced material waste [16]. Several researchers have investigated the influence of AM process parameters, demonstrating their strong impact on porosity and water absorption capacity, which are critical for heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) applications [17,18]. In this context, recent studies have explored a hybrid air cooling system combining desiccant wheel manufactured by AM, highlighting the potential of additively manufactured porous structures for enhancing moisture [19]. More recently, the use of lattice geometries fabricated via AM has gained attention, as they provide enhanced surface area and improved airflow distribution [20,21]. Studies have demonstrated that increasing the surface area density of lattice channels, while keeping the relative volume constant, leads to a marked improvement in cooling effectiveness [22].

Several experimental studies have reported significant performance parameters in cooling systems. For instance, a modified DEC system employing a luffa fibre cooling pad achieved a temperature drop of approximately 11 °C and a cooling effectiveness exceeding 84 % under

hot ambient conditions [23]. Similarly, a comparative investigation of various plant-based pads in Sub-Saharan climates showed saturation efficiencies above 70 % and stable cooling capacities under moderate to high air flow velocities [24]. More recently, wet channels manufactured by AM using foam polymeric materials demonstrated that the most with porous configuration achieved the lowest supply air temperature and the highest sensible power [25]. In this context, experimental and numerical investigations on wet channels manufactured with polymeric film materials have demonstrated their suitability for evaporative cooling applications, highlighting the strong coupling between material properties, geometric factors and cooling performance [26]. In addition, lattice ceramic structures have been shown to enhance thermal performance in compact heat exchangers (HX) by increasing specific surface area, thereby improving sensible heat transfer, although often at the cost of higher pressure drop [27]. Recent investigations on gyroid HX have further confirmed the high heat and mass-transfer potential of these geometries, resulting to their continuous surface and interconnected pore networks [28]. However, current literature lacks a systematic and quantitative assessment of how lattice geometry, surface development and material wettability jointly influence evaporative effectiveness when used as DEC pad media. Moreover, no previous studies have integrated material characterization, mesoscale geometric analysis, and full-scale prototype validation under controlled boundary conditions. This gap limits the ability to rationally design architected pads that maximise cooling performance while minimising pressure losses and material usage.

Despite the growing research on AM and lattice geometries with polymeric materials, their application in evaporative cooling systems remains largely unexplored, particularly regarding the energy performance of cooling pads. AM provides significant advantages for these systems, such as the ability to tailor geometries to specific design requirements, optimize surface area for enhanced heat and mass transfer, and incorporate recycled composites, making it an especially promising approach for sustainable cooling solutions. The main objectives of this study are: (i) to characterize the morphological, textural and wetting

properties of the PLA-wood composite and assess their suitability for evaporative cooling; (ii) to design and fabricate architected cooling pads with identical external volume and controlled lattice geometry; (iii) to experimentally compare the five configurations under fixed inlet conditions and identify the geometric features that maximise heat and mass transfer; (iv) to upscale the most efficient design into a functional prototype with integrated water distribution; and (v) to evaluate the influence of inlet air temperature and airflow rate through a DOE-based statistical analysis. Overall, this study provides a systematic experimental evaluation of additively manufactured PLA-wood composite lattices for evaporative cooling applications. By integrating material characterization, controlled lattice design and energy performance analysis under fixed operating conditions, this work offers a comprehensive framework to understand the coupled effects of composite behaviour and architected geometry on cooling efficiency. The results highlight the potential of AM to engineer next-generation evaporative pads with improved cooling capacity, higher wet-bulb effectiveness, and more efficient use of material.

2. Methodology

2.1. Characterization of materials

The material selected for this study was a composite filament made of PLA (80 wt. %) and pinewood particles (20 wt. %), commercially supplied by Smart Materials 3D (Jaén, Spain). This biocomposite was selected for its suitability in AM and its potential in evaporative cooling systems, where porosity and water retention capacity play a critical role. Specimens were fabricated using MEX technique, a widely used form of AM, employing a Creality Ender 3 printer (Shenzhen, China). To evaluate their morphological, textural, and surface properties, the specimens were subsequently subjected to a set of characterization tests, including Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms, and wettability analysis. The microstructure of the specimens was examined using SEM with a JSM-7800F microscope (Jeol, Japan), to observe morphological features and pore architecture. In addition, the porosity was characterized through nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms, conducted at 77 K using a Micromeritics 3Flex Surface Characterization system (Canon, Japan). The isotherms were recorded over a relative pressure range (P/P_0) from 0.01 to 0.99, enabling the determination of specific surface area, pore volume, and pore size distribution.

The material surface wettability was characterized by measuring static and dynamic contact angles of water drops deposited on the samples in ambient air. Measurements were carried out on square specimens with dimensions of approximately 20 mm × 20 mm × 10 mm. Water drops of controlled volume were generated using a high-precision syringe pump to ensure repeatable deposition conditions. The samples were placed on a horizontally aligned support, and each drop was illuminated from the rear using a diffuse light source to enhance the contrast of the liquid-air interface. Side-view images of the drops were acquired immediately after deposition using a high-resolution digital camera equipped with a macro lens. The acquired images were processed using dedicated image analysis routines to extract the drop contour and the solid-liquid baseline. Static contact angles on horizontal surfaces were determined using an axisymmetric drop shape analysis approach. In this method, the theoretical profile of an axisymmetric drop, obtained through the Laplace-Young equation, is numerically fitted to the experimental contour, extracted from image processing, following the Axisymmetric Drop Shape Analysis-Perimeter technique [29,30], which accounts for the balance between surface tension and gravitational forces. Once the fitted profile and the baseline are identified, the static contact angle is evaluated as the angle between the tangent to the fitted profile and the solid surface at the contact line. Dynamic contact angles were evaluated on vertical surfaces, where the gravitational force induces asymmetric drop shapes. As the drops

remained adhered to the surface in the vertical orientation, after deposition the drop profile was allowed to stabilize, and side-view images were acquired to capture the liquid-air interface. The advancing and receding contact angles were then estimated by independently analyzing the upper and lower contact regions through linear fitting of the two extreme interface segments over a length selected to be representative while ensuring negligible curvature effects. Both approaches described above have been successfully applied in previous studies on materials used for evaporative cooling applications [31,32], and further details on the image processing techniques and on the associated measurement uncertainty are reported in [33].

2.2. Design and manufacturing of cooling pads

Five different internal geometries were selected to evaluate the influence of structural design on evaporative cooling performance. Four pads incorporated distinct lattice configurations, X-shaped (P1), star-shaped (P2), octagonal (P3), and soft-box (P4), chosen for their markedly different distributions of specific surface area, flow tortuosity, leading to distinct airflow paths and air-water interaction mechanisms, which directly influence evaporative heat and mass transfer. A conventional grid configuration (P5) was used as a reference. The geometries were designed in Autodesk Netfabb, and Fig. 1 illustrates the internal design corresponding to the five configurations.

Five cooling pads were fabricated via MEX using the previously characterized PLA-wood biocomposite. To ensure consistent comparison across designs, all pads were manufactured with identical external dimensions (50 mm × 50 mm × 100 mm) and a unit cell size of 6 mm. This unit cell size was selected as a compromise between surface area enhancement and airflow resistance, and is consistent with values reported in additively manufactured heat exchangers [34]. This approach ensured that differences in performance could be attributed solely to the internal architecture and the resulting development of air-water contact area. The printing configuration and slicing process were carried out using Ultimaker Cura software (v.5.2.1) [35]. Printing parameters and material composition were selected based on a previous optimization study identifying the PLA-wood formulation with the highest water vapour adsorption capacity [17]. The detailed printing conditions are summarized in Table 1.

Based on the experimental evaluation of the five geometries, the octagonal lattice configuration was selected and scaled up to develop a full-scale prototype, as it exhibited the highest temperature drop and wet-bulb effectiveness among the tested designs. The final design maintained the same lattice characteristics but increased the external dimensions to 100 mm × 100 mm × 120 mm (width × height × length). This prototype incorporated an internal water-distribution system to ensure continuous wetting of the channels and maximise evaporative efficiency under practical operating conditions. Fig. 2 presents the design of the full-scale prototype, illustrating the internal lattice structure and integrated water-feeding configuration. Inlet and outlet connector interfaces were incorporated into the model to allow direct attachment to air ducts.

2.3. Experimental setup

An experimental setup was designed and implemented to assess the evaporative performance of the cooling systems (Fig. 3): for the cooling pads and for the full-scale prototype. All experiments were conducted at the HVAC Laboratory of the University of Córdoba. An Air Handling Unit (AHU) was used to accurately regulate the inlet air conditions, including temperature, humidity, and airflow rate. In the first stage, the five cooling pads were tested under fixed inlet conditions with an air temperature (T_i) of 45 °C, an airflow rate of 33 m³/h, and a dew point temperature of 14 °C. In the second stage, the setup was adapted to the full-scale prototype which incorporated a continuous water supply system. In this configuration, both the inlet air temperature and airflow rate

Fig. 1. Internal architecture of the five additively manufactured lattice geometries (P1–P5) designed using Autodesk Netfabb. The upper row shows the three-dimensional perspective views, while the lower row presents the corresponding frontal views.

Table 1
Printing parameters used to manufacture the cooling pads.

Printing parameters	Value
Layer height [mm]	0.2
Nozzle temperature [°C]	215
Build plate temperature [°C]	80
Printing speed [mm/s]	50
Nozzle diameter [mm]	0.4
Flow [%]	100
Printing acceleration [mm/s ²]	500

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the full-scale prototype, illustrating the airflow path from inlet to outlet and the integrated water circulation system, including the top water supply and bottom drainage for continuous wetting of the lattice module.

were varied, as summarized in Table 3. Airflow rate was measured using a Pitot tube (PT), while Flow Conditioners (FC) were installed upstream and downstream of the experimental section to ensure a uniform and fully developed airflow profile at the outlet of the AHU. Air temperature, relative humidity, and pressure drop were measured at the inlet and outlet of the evaporative cooling system, as indicated in Fig. 3.

Both systems were equipped with calibrated sensors to measure dry-bulb temperature (T), dew point temperature (T_d), and pressure drop (ΔP) across the sample. Sensor specifications are provided in Table 2.

2.4. Experimental procedure

The experimental testing procedure was carried out in two distinct stages: (i) In the first stage, each of the five cooling pad was initially weighed in its dry state, then fully submerged in water for 30 min to

ensure complete saturation. After immersion, excess surface water was removed, and the wet weight was recorded. The saturated sample was then placed on the experimental setup (see Fig. 3) and exposed to a controlled airstream with fixed inlet conditions: an air temperature of 45 °C, a volumetric flow rate of 33 m³/h, and an inlet dew point temperature of 14 °C. Each experiment lasted 13 min, during which the outlet dry-bulb temperature and humidity ratio were recorded at 1-minute intervals. These trials were designed to evaluate the evaporative performance of the five different pad geometries under quasi-steady-state conditions. (ii) In the second stage, a full-scale prototype was tested, fabricated using the most efficient lattice geometry identified during the first phase. Unlike the small-scale samples, the prototype incorporated an integrated water supply system that continuously distributed water through internal channels, ensuring consistent saturation throughout the experiment. The prototype was positioned directly on the experimental setup and evaluated under a broader range of operating conditions. A multilevel design of experiments (DOE) approach was employed, varying the inlet air temperature across six levels (20, 25, 30, 35, 40, and 45 °C) and the airflow rate between 90 m³/h and 120 m³/h, as detailed in Table 3.

A statistical analysis based on Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to evaluate the effect of inlet conditions on the cooling performance of the full-scale prototype. This approach made it possible to identify and quantify the most influential operating parameters, including inlet air temperature (T_i) and airflow rate (\dot{V}_i), and their impact on response variables such as outlet dry-bulb temperature (T_o), dew point temperature ($T_{d,o}$) and pressure drop (ΔP). The experimental data were fitted using a second-order polynomial regression model described by Eq. (1), where \hat{Y} represents the predicted response variable, and the coefficients β are estimated through regression analysis.

$$\hat{Y} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot T_i + \beta_2 \cdot \dot{V}_i + \beta_3 \cdot T_i^2 + \beta_4 \cdot \dot{V}_i^2 + \beta_5 \cdot T_i \cdot \dot{V}_i \tag{1}$$

2.5. Heat transfer and performance parameters

The parameters used to evaluate the performance of the cooling pads and the full-scale prototype are listed below:

- A contact surface-to-volume ratio (R) was defined, as shown in Eq. (2). This parameter was calculated as the quotient of the contact surface, that is the area available for air–water interaction (S_c), and the total external volume ($V = 250 \text{ cm}^3$).

$$R = \frac{S_c}{V} \tag{2}$$

- The sensible cooling heat (\dot{Q}_s) provided by the pad was calculated based on the air mass flow rate (\dot{m}) and the change in specific enthalpy between the auxiliary (h_{aux}) and an inlet air (h_i) reference state (Eq. (3)).

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the experimental setup used to evaluate the performance. The system includes the components and sensors installed upstream and downstream of the test section.

Table 2
Technical specifications of the sensors.

Variable	Type of sensor	Accuracy
T	Thermocouple type T	± 0.5 °C
T _d	Chilled mirror hygrometer	± 0.15 °C
ΔP	Differential pressure transmitter	± 5 %

Table 3
Design of experiments.

Experiment	T _i [°C]	T _{d,i} [°C]	Ṃ _i [m ³ /h]
1	20	14	90
2	25	14	90
3	30	14	90
4	35	14	90
5	40	14	90
6	45	14	90
7	20	14	120
8	25	14	120
9	30	14	120
10	35	14	120
11	40	14	120
12	45	14	120

The auxiliary enthalpy corresponds to a hypothetical psychrometric state defined to separate the sensible and latent heat contributions. This state is defined as having the same dry-bulb temperature as the outlet air and the same humidity ratio as the inlet air. Therefore, the enthalpy difference $h_{aux} - h_i$ represents purely the sensible heat transfer, while the remaining enthalpy change is associated with latent heat due to evaporation.

$$\dot{Q}_s = \dot{m} \cdot (h_{aux} - h_i) \quad (3)$$

• The latent heat (\dot{Q}_l) corresponds to the energy required for water evaporation from the wetted surface into the airflow, resulting in an increase in the air humidity ratio. It was calculated according to Eq. (4) as the product of the air mass flow rate (\dot{m}) and the difference in specific enthalpy between the outlet air (h_o) and the auxiliary state (h_{aux}). Therefore, the term $h_o - h_{aux}$ represents the latent contribution of the total enthalpy change.

$$\dot{Q}_l = \dot{m} \cdot (h_o - h_{aux}) \quad (4)$$

• Electric energy consumption of the fan (\dot{W}_{fan}) was calculated as the product of the pressure drop (ΔP) and the inlet airflow rate (\dot{V}_i) divided by the fan efficiency (η_{fan}) considered 0.5, obtained with Eq. (5):

$$\dot{W}_{fan} = \frac{\Delta P \cdot \dot{V}_i}{\eta_{fan}} \quad (5)$$

• The energy efficiency ratio (EER) evaluates the cooling performance relative to the electrical energy consumption. It is defined as the ratio between the sensible cooling heat (\dot{Q}_s) and the electrical energy consumption of the fan (\dot{W}_{fan}) and the pump (\dot{W}_{pump}), which was considered constant (4 W) according to Eq. (6):

$$EER = \frac{\dot{Q}_s}{\dot{W}_{fan} + \dot{W}_{pump}} \quad (6)$$

• The wet-bulb effectiveness (ϵ_{wb}) provides a non-dimensional indicator of the system's performance, defined as the ratio between the difference of inlet (T_i) and outlet (T_o) dry bulb temperatures and the difference between (T_i) and inlet wet bulb temperature ($T_{wb,i}$), obtained with Eq. (7):

$$\epsilon_{wb} = \frac{T_i - T_o}{T_i - T_{wb,i}} \quad (7)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Surface characterization of the material

3.1.1. Scanning electron microscopy

Fig. 4 shows the SEM microstructure of the PLA-wood composite material, taken at a magnification of 100. The deposited layers showed no significant delamination or gaps between filaments, indicating consistent extrusion and proper interlayer bonding. The surface texture was notably rough and irregular, displaying multiple micropores and crevices. Based on qualitative observations, such surface features promote water retention and enhance air–water interaction, which can contribute to evaporative cooling performance.

3.1.2. Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherm

Nitrogen adsorption–desorption analysis was conducted to evaluate the textural properties of the composite material selected. The isotherm obtained is presented in Fig. 5a, is a type-IV curve with a pronounced hysteresis loop, which is characteristic of mesoporous materials and

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of the PLA-wood biocomposite filament surface, showing the morphology. The inset highlights localized porosity and microstructural features at higher magnification.

Fig. 5. (a) Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms of the selected composite material. (b) Cumulative pore volume and pore size distribution $dV/d\log(W)$ as a function of pore width.

indicates capillary condensation within interconnected pores. The maximum adsorption capacity achieved was $0.14 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ at a relative pressure of $P/P_0 = 0.99$, this interpretation is consistent with the low intrinsic microporosity of PLA-based composites. The BET surface area of the material was measured as $0.1213 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, indicating that the accessible surface is primarily associated with mesoporous features and surface textural characteristics.

The cumulative pore volume as a function of pore width is shown in Fig. 5b. The cumulative pore volume (blue curve) demonstrated a rapid increase in pore volume at smaller pore widths (1–50 Å), confirming a significant presence of mesopores. The differential pore volume distribution (orange curve) also revealed a major contribution from pores below 100 Å, and showed a dominant peak near 50 Å, supporting the role of these mesopores in capillary-driven water retention and stabilization of liquid films across the printed. Table 4 summarized the key quantitative values derived from the nitrogen physisorption results.

Table 4
Surface properties.

	Total pore volume [cm^3/g]	Average pore diameter [Å]
Adsorption	0.000174	57.391
Desorption	0.000049	16.113

3.2. Wettability analysis

For the wettability experiments, the surfaces exhibited anisotropic roughness due to the presence of grooves and micropores formed during the 3D printing process, and these surface irregularities may play an important role in the wettability of the material, directly affecting the contact angle of water with the surface and, consequently, its ability to spread or be absorbed. If the micropores are in practice uniformly distributed, the grooves, aligned with the printing direction, induce a “pinning” effect that elongates the drop profile and modifies the apparent contact angles, as reported in previous studies [36]. Therefore,

the specimens were investigated in three different configurations: i) Horizontal surface, with the surface microgrooves oriented parallel to the camera lens. ii) Horizontal surface, with the surface microgrooves oriented perpendicular to the camera lens. iii) Vertical surface, with the surface microgrooves oriented perpendicular to the camera lens.

Although the pinning effect breaks the ideal axisymmetry of the drop, previous work [37] shows that ADSA-P remains valid when groove dimensions are small relative to drop size. For each specimen and configuration, ten drops (with volume $11 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^3$) were deposited and processed to ensure the repeatability of the results. Fig. 6 shows three examples of drops, on a horizontal surface (Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b) and on a vertical surface (Fig. 6c), respectively.

It is already visually evident that the drop in the perpendicular orientation appears taller, indicating a higher contact angle, whereas the drop in the parallel orientation is more spread out, corresponding to a lower contact angle.

Fig. 7 shows a boxplot chart reporting the results for the static contact angle (θ) analysis, on horizontal surfaces. The central line inside each box corresponds to the median value of the dataset, while the cross indicates the mean. The edges of the box represent the first and third quartiles, and the whiskers extend to the maximum and minimum values.

The values in perpendicular orientation are significantly larger than those in parallel orientation, reaching the range of hydrophobicity (contact angles larger than 90°). The overall mean of the contact angle values is 81° , with a standard deviation of 4° , for the parallel orientation, and 110° , with a standard deviation of 7° , for the perpendicular one. The median values, which are very close to the mean values, are 82° and 110° for the parallel and perpendicular configuration, respectively, thus evidencing the absence of distorting effects of possible extreme values.

Fig. 8 shows the results for the dynamic angles evaluated on the surfaces in vertical orientation. The receding contact angles are consistently lower than the advancing ones, with the static angles enclosed in the range between these two. The overall mean of the receding angles is 62° (with a standard deviation of 11°), that of the advancing ones is 114° (with a standard deviation of 7°). The median values of the advancing and receding contact angles are 62° and 115° , respectively, and differ from the corresponding mean values by $<1^\circ$, suggesting no significant bias toward extreme values. In this case, the standard deviations are larger than those obtained in the static contact angle analysis, mainly due to the limitations of linear fitting and the difficulty in achieving perfect drop alignment. Contact angle hysteresis, calculated as the difference between advancing and receding contact angles, has mean value 52° , median value 52° , and standard deviation 10° .

Overall, these results indicate an intermediate wettability regime, consistent with the behaviour desirable in porous evaporative media. This balance between capillary imbibition and limited spreading enhances water retention while maintaining high evaporation rates [18], confirming the suitability of the PLA-wood composite for evaporative

cooling applications.

3.3. Cooling pad manufacturing

After completing the material characterization, five evaporative cooling pads were fabricated. Four pads incorporated distinct lattice geometries, namely, X-shaped (P1), star-shaped (P2), octagonal (P3), soft box (P4), and also the reference grid geometry (P5), as illustrated in Fig. 9. All pads were designed with identical external dimensions, resulting in a constant total volume of 250 cm^3 .

To evaluate the geometric efficiency of each design, three key parameters were considered: (i) dry weight (w_d), to assess material usage and density differences; (ii) contact surface (S_c): obtained from the digital models, representing the area available for air–water interaction, and (iii) contact surface-to-volume ratio (R) calculated using Eq. (2). This ratio provided a comparative metric of the available surface per unit volume, which is essential for assessing the potential for evaporation and heat and mass transfer. The values for each pad are summarized in Table 5.

Among the evaluated geometries, pad P3 exhibited the highest S_c and R, while also achieving the lowest w_d , indicating the most efficient surface development with minimal material usage. In contrast, pad P5 showed the lowest S_c and R and the highest w_d , reflecting the least favourable configuration in terms of surface efficiency relative to material usage. This comparison indicated that lattice structures clearly outperform conventional grid geometries in terms of surface generation efficiency and structural economy for evaporative media applications.

3.4. Energy analysis

3.4.1. Cooling pads performance

Experiments were carried out to evaluate the performance of five different cooling pads under controlled conditions. The psychrometric trajectories for each configuration are shown in Fig. 10. The white circle indicates the inlet air condition, which remained constant during all experiments, while the coloured lines represent the temporal evolution of the outlet air properties for each pad during the 13-minute experiment.

At the beginning of the experiment, the dry-bulb temperature decreased progressively while the humidity ratio increased, driven by water evaporation from the fully saturated pad media. As the process progressed, each curve reached a minimum temperature and a peak humidity ratio. This stage corresponded to the period of highest cooling efficiency, when the material's surface was fully saturated and optimal air–water contact was maintained. Beyond this point, as the pad began to dry and less water was available for evaporation, the cooling capacity diminished. This was reflected by a gradual increase in outlet air temperature and a stabilization, or even a slight decline, in humidity ratio.

Among the tested pads, P3 demonstrated the highest cooling capacity, reaching the lowest outlet temperature of 25.3°C and the highest

Fig. 6. Water drops images on horizontal surface in (a) “parallel” and (b) “perpendicular” orientations and on (c) a vertical surface.

Fig. 7. Boxplot of the static contact angle for the different specimens, in parallel and perpendicular orientations.

Fig. 8. Boxplot of the dynamic contact angles for the different specimens in vertical orientation.

humidity ratio ($0.0153 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). Its trajectory approached more closely the adiabatic saturation line, indicating a more efficient conversion of

Fig. 9. Additively manufactured PLA–wood composite cooling pads corresponding to the five lattice configurations: P1 (X), P2 (Star), P3 (Octagon), P4 (Soft box) and P5 (Grid), arranged from left to right.

Table 5

Geometric parameters of the five cooling pad designs, including dry weight (w_d), contact surface (S_c), and contact surface-to-volume ratio (R).

Pads	w_d [g]	S_c [cm ²]	R [cm ⁻¹]
P1	67.0	860.9	3.4
P2	75.4	926.5	3.7
P3	60.6	1612.1	6.4
P4	73.3	1133.8	4.5
P5	102.9	583.2	2.3

sensible heat into latent heat through evaporation and confirming a superior cooling effectiveness. This behaviour is directly related to the structural characteristics reported in Table 5, where P3 exhibited the largest available surface area for mass transfer. A higher S_c provided a greater wetted interface for heat and mass exchange, enhancing evaporation and supporting better water retention within the pad structure. Additionally, its higher R increased the effective contact between air and

water, enabling faster heat absorption and sustained evaporation. Together, these properties allowed P3 to maintain a fully wetted state for a longer period, resulting in a more prolonged and effective cooling process.

Pads P2 and P4 exhibited an intermediate performance between P3 and the lower-performing designs. Their lattice structures provided a substantial increase in surface area compared to the reference (P5), enabling effective evaporative cooling during the initial and intermediate stages of the experiment. However, their psychrometric trajectories deviated earlier from the saturation line compared to P3, suggesting less uniform water distribution and the onset of localized drying within specific flow paths.

In contrast, the trajectories of pads P1 and P5 exhibited more limited cooling effects, reaching minimum outlet temperatures of 27.4 °C and 30.9 °C, respectively, and returning more rapidly toward the inlet condition. This behaviour indicated faster drying of the medium and a reduced capacity to retain water within internal structures. These trends were also consistent with the properties in Table 5, where both P1 and P5

Fig. 10. Psychrometric chart showing the evolution of outlet air conditions for the five lattice configurations under identical inlet conditions (marked with a white circle).

had the smallest air–water contact areas. As a result, the reduced interface area limited the duration and intensity of the evaporative effect during the final stages of the experiments. In particular, the reference P5 exhibited the least effective air–water interaction, confirming the relevance of geometric design in enhancing evaporative heat and mass transfer. All measurement were repeated three times, and similar trends were observed in every case, reinforcing the repeatability and robustness of the results.

The influence of the contact surface-to-volume ratio (R), is illustrated in Fig. 11, defined in Eq. (2) and summarized in Table 5, on two key performance indicators of the cooling pads: the maximum temperature drop between inlet and outlet air (ΔT_{\max}) and the total accumulated cooling energy (Q) during the 13-min experimental period. A clear positive correlation was observed between R and both ΔT_{\max} and Q , indicating that pads with a higher geometric development of surface area were able to exchange heat and mass more efficiently. As R increased, the pads achieved greater temperature reductions and higher total cooling energy

Pad P3, which exhibited the highest R , achieved the largest temperature drop (19.7 °C) and the greatest accumulated cooling energy (2352 J), confirming its superior heat and mass transfer effectiveness. Its high surface-to-volume ratio promoted more homogeneous wetting and delayed local dry-out, allowing evaporation to be sustained over a longer fraction of the experiment duration. Conversely, P5, with the lowest R , recorded the smallest ΔT_{\max} and energy output, confirming that limited contact surface and lower geometric complexity reduce evaporative capacity by restricting air–water interaction.

Pads P1, P2 and P4 exhibited intermediate values of R and correspondingly intermediate cooling performance. Although all three designs benefited from increased surface development compared to P5, differences in lattice topology influenced how effectively this surface area was exploited.

The evolution of wet bulb effectiveness (ϵ_{wb}) over time for the five cooling pads is shown in Fig. 12. All samples exhibited an initial increase in effectiveness during the first minutes of operation, reaching a peak because the pads were fully saturated, followed by a gradual decline associated with the progressive drying of the medium and the consequent reduction in evaporative capacity. This behaviour followed an inverse trend to that observed in the outlet dry-bulb temperature.

Among all pads, P3 exhibited the highest and most stable performance, reaching a maximum effectiveness of 0.93. Its superior and

sustained evaporative response during the first half of the experiment is consistent with its larger air–water contact area (Table 5) and with the psychrometric trajectories presented in Fig. 10, where P3 achieved the greatest cooling effect and moisture gain. In contrast, P1 reached a lower peak effectiveness of 0.83, while the reference pad P5 attained only 0.66, showing a faster and more pronounced decline over time. These results confirm that all lattice-type geometries outperformed the reference grid design, demonstrating higher wet-bulb effectiveness and a more stable evaporative response, when water availability and surface wetting were critical. Pads P2 and P4 exhibited intermediate wet-bulb effectiveness values and temporal stability between P3 and the lower-performing designs. Both geometries achieved relatively high peak effectiveness during the initial saturated stage, but their effectiveness declined earlier than that of P3, indicating a less uniform or less persistent wetting of the internal structure.

Higher wet-bulb effectiveness is achieved when a well-distributed wetted surface remains in contact with the airflow and water is supplied and retained in a gradual manner, sustaining evaporation over time. Conversely, uneven wetting or rapid water depletion promotes early dry-out, reducing the effective air–water interface and limiting wet-bulb effectiveness.

3.4.2. Full-scale prototype performance

Based on the energy performance analysis of the five cooling pads, the lattice geometry P3, which exhibited the highest evaporative effectiveness, was selected for the development of a full-scale prototype. This prototype, shown in Fig. 13, was designed with an integrated water distribution system. It features dedicated inlet and outlet connections for airflow, a water supply inlet at the top feeding the internal channels to ensure continuous wetting during operation, and a drain outlet at the bottom to collect excess water. Small side sealed perforations were also included to accommodate temperature and humidity sensors during testing. A detailed view of the internal lattice structure is also provided on the right side of Fig. 13.

The temperature drop between inlet and outlet air (ΔT) is shown in Fig. 14, corresponding to the instant when the minimum outlet temperature was achieved, as a function of the inlet air temperature (T_i) for two inlet airflow rates ($\dot{V}_i = 90 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and $\dot{V}_i = 120 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$).

In both cases, ΔT increased almost linearly with T_i , indicating that higher inlet temperatures enhanced the driving potential for evaporation and, consequently, the cooling capacity of the system. At the same

Fig. 11. Effect of the contact surface-to-volume ratio (R) on the maximum temperature drop (ΔT_{\max}) and total accumulated cooling energy (Q) for each cooling pad.

Fig. 12. Evolution of wet bulb effectiveness (ϵ_{wb}) over the test time for the five cooling pads.

Fig. 13. Full-scale prototype fabricated with the P3 lattice geometry. The model includes air inlet and outlet ducts, a top water supply inlet. On the right the internal lattice structure.

inlet temperature, the higher \dot{V}_i consistently produced greater temperature differences than the lower one. This behaviour was attributed to the higher mass flow of air through the pad, which increased the overall rate of heat and mass transfer while maintaining sufficient contact time for effective evaporation. For instance, at $T_i = 45^\circ\text{C}$, the temperature drop reached 21.2°C for $\dot{V}_i = 120\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, compared to 18.7°C for $\dot{V}_i = 90\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. Overall, higher airflow rate led to greater cooling effectiveness of the full-scale prototype.

A DOE was performed to evaluate the performance of the full-scale prototype (see Table 3). This approach enabled the development of an ANOVA and a second-order polynomial regression model (Eq. (1)), to describe the relationship between the inlet air temperature (T_i) and

airflow rate (V) as input variables, and the outlet dry-bulb temperature (T_o), outlet dew point temperature ($T_{d,o}$), and pressure drop across the pad (ΔP) as response variables.

Table 6 presents the estimated regression coefficients (β_n) along with their standard errors, F-ratios, and corresponding p-values. For T_o , both linear and quadratic terms of T_i and \dot{V}_i were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming their strong influence on heat exchange, whereas the interaction term $T_i \cdot \dot{V}_i$ was not significant ($p = 0.1382$). In the case of $T_{d,o}$, the airflow rate and its interaction with temperature exhibited highly significant effects, whereas temperature alone showed only marginal influence ($p = 0.0609$). Regarding ΔP , only the quadratic term of \dot{V}_i^2 showed statistical significance ($p = 0.0059$), indicating that airflow rate

Fig. 14. Dry-bulb temperature drop (ΔT) between inlet and outlet air as a function of the inlet air temperature (T_i) for two airflow rates (90 and 120 m^3/h) in the full-scale prototype experiments.

Table 6
Estimated coefficients (β_n) and effects of input variables on output variables obtained from ANOVA.

T_o				
Effect	Estimated coefficients (β_n)	Std. error	F-ratio	P-value
Intercept	0.004	0.28		
T_i	0.497	1.29	20.19	0.0028
\dot{V}_i	0.224	1.85	41.66	0.0003
T_i^2	-0.004	0.78	7.32	0.0303
\dot{V}_i^2	-0.002	1.94	45.55	0.0003
$T_i \cdot \dot{V}_i$	0.001	0.48	2.79	0.1382
R^2				0.9961
$T_{d,o}$				
Effect	Coefficient estimated (β_n)	Std. error	F-ratio	P-value
Intercept	0.006	0.39		
T_i	-0.335	0.87	4.97	0.0609
\dot{V}_i	0.321	2.66	46.39	0.0002
T_i^2	0.001	0.12	0.10	0.7535
\dot{V}_i^2	-0.002	2.58	43.63	0.0003
$T_i \cdot \dot{V}_i$	0.005	2.23	32.55	0.0007
R^2				0.9801
ΔP				
Effect	Coefficient estimated (β_n)	Std. error	F-ratio	P-value
Intercept	0.015			
T_i	-1.827	4.75	1.77	0.2241
\dot{V}_i	0.765	6.35	3.16	0.1182
T_i^2	-0.001	0.31	0.01	0.9334
\dot{V}_i^2	0.012	13.86	15.12	0.0059
$T_i \cdot \dot{V}_i$	0.010	4.56	1.63	0.2413
R^2				0.9975

predominantly governs the pressure losses across the pad. The high coefficients of determination ($R^2 > 0.98$) obtained for all three models confirm the robustness of the fits and validate the reliability of the experimental design.

The effect of the input variables on the three responses variables is visually summarized in Fig. 15. The influence of T_i is shown in Fig. 15a, where increasing T_i leads to a clear rise in both T_o and $T_{d,o}$ consistent with the significant linear trend identified in the ANOVA results (Table 6). This behaviour suggested enhanced heat and moisture transfer under higher inlet temperatures. Conversely, in Fig. 15b,

increasing \dot{V}_i results in a moderate decrease in T_o indicating improved cooling capacity. However, this comes at the cost of a pronounced increase in ΔP which grows steeply with \dot{V}_i as also reflected by the significant quadratic term in the ANOVA.

The response surfaces shown in Fig. 16 illustrate the combined influence of T_i and \dot{V}_i on the thermal performance of the full-scale prototype. In Fig. 16a and Fig. 16b, both sensible cooling heat (\dot{Q}_s) and latent heat (\dot{Q}_l) increased with rising \dot{V}_i and T_i . The influence of airflow rate is predominant, but the effect of temperature is also evident in the sensible component. Thus, latent heat transfer is mainly controlled by airflow rate, whereas inlet temperature primarily influences the sensible cooling component. The highest cooling heat was obtained at the maximum airflow rate (120 m^3/h) and inlet temperature (45 °C), reaching total heat removal values close to 822 W, whereas the minimum occurred at 90 m^3/h and 20 °C, with approximately 61 W. Fig. 16c shows the corresponding electric energy consumption of the fan (\dot{W}_{fan}), which increased mainly with \dot{V}_i , ranging from 6 W at 90 m^3/h to 16 W at 120 m^3/h , while remaining nearly unaffected by inlet temperature. This behaviour reflects the higher pressure losses through the pad at greater airflow rates, requiring additional mechanical work to maintain the flow. Hence, although higher ventilation enhances the cooling potential, it also entails a proportional rise in electrical consumption. Fig. 16d presents the energy efficiency ratio (EER), which increased with inlet temperature (T_i) for both airflow rates. The EER values ranged from 8 to 86, at 90 m^3/h and from 7 to 53 at 120 m^3/h . For a given T_i , the lower airflow rate consistently produced higher EER values, indicating that although increasing airflow enhances the cooling capacity, it also raises the fan power consumption, reducing overall energy efficiency.

4. Conclusions

This work presented a comprehensive experimental evaluation of five evaporative cooling pads manufactured from a PLA-wood composite, including four lattice-based designs and one reference grid geometry. The study integrated material characterization, geometric analysis and system-level energy evaluation to identify the structural features governing evaporative performance. The main conclusions are:

- The material analysis showed that SEM images revealed a rough and irregular surface morphology with micropores, enhancing the effective surface area for water retention and evaporation. The nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms demonstrated the presence

Fig. 15. Effect of inlet dry-bulb air temperature on: (a) outlet dry-bulb air temperature, (b) outlet dew point air temperature, and (c) pressure drop at constant airflow rate. Effect of inlet airflow rate on: (d) outlet dry-bulb air temperature, (e) outlet dew point air temperature, and (f) pressure drop at constant inlet air temperature.

Fig. 16. Response surfaces of the energy performance of the prototype as a function of inlet air temperature and inlet airflow rate: (a) Sensible cooling heat, (b) latent heat, (c) electric energy consumption of the fan and (d) energy efficiency ratio.

of mesopores, supporting capillary condensation and further promoting air–water interaction. Wettability measurements indicated an intermediate wetting behaviour, favourable for water imbibition without hindering evaporation. Together, these findings confirm the suitability of the PLA-wood composite as an engineered material for architected evaporative media.

- The energy analysis confirmed the strong influence of lattice geometry on evaporative performance. The octagonal design (P3) achieved the best results, reaching the lowest outlet temperature (25.3 °C), the highest wet-bulb effectiveness (0.93), and the largest accumulated cooling energy (2352 J). This superior behaviour can be attributed to its higher surface-to-volume ratio and more uniform pore connectivity, which increase air–water contact time and enhance the conversion of sensible heat into latent heat through evaporation. Compared to the reference pad, these values represent a substantial improvement, highlighting the pivotal role of surface development and geometric tortuosity in sustaining evaporation and delaying media drying. In contrast, geometries with lower specific surface area or straighter airflow paths experienced reduced interaction time and faster depletion of retained water. Pads with lower contact areas (P1 and P5) dried out more rapidly and showed limited cooling effectiveness.
- The full-scale prototype was fabricated with the best-performing octagonal lattice geometry (P3). The integrated water distribution system provided homogeneous saturation of the medium, allowing stable and continuous operation. The statistical analysis (ANOVA) confirmed that both inlet air temperature (T_i) and airflow rate (\dot{V}_i) had significant effects on the cooling responses, particularly on outlet temperatures and pressure drop. Higher airflow rates enhanced cooling capacity by increasing the mass flow of dry air interacting with the wetted lattice, but at the expense of higher pressure losses due to increased flow resistance. Furthermore, the response surface models for \dot{Q}_e , \dot{Q}_l , W , and EER, provided predictive capability and identified operating regions where cooling performance and energy efficiency were maximised, with maximum EER values reaching 86.7 at 45 °C and 90 m³/h.

Overall, this study provides the first systematic experimental evidence of the significant influence of internal lattice geometry on the heat and mass transfer behaviour of evaporative pads and confirmed the feasibility of scaling the optimized design into a functional prototype. Beyond the experimental findings, this work demonstrates the practical potential of AM-enabled architected pads to enhance the performance, durability and design flexibility of evaporative cooling systems in HVAC applications. The ability to tailor lattice geometry, surface area density and material usage provides a pathway for designing next-generation evaporative media with higher cooling capacity and improved energy efficiency. Future work may explore multi-material AM approaches, larger-scale industrial designs, and geometry optimisation strategies to further advance sustainable evaporative cooling technologies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Paula Conrat: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Francisco Comino:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Roberta Caruana:** Resources, Investigation. **Manfredo Guilizzoni:** Resources, Investigation. **Pablo E. Romero:** Investigation. **Manuel Ruiz de Adana:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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